

SOMATOMETRIC BODY INDICATORS OF REPRESENTATIVES OF VARIOUS SPORTS

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ABSTRACT

The human body's adaptation to intense physical activity is a key issue in muscle physiology and sports medicine. This issue's significance is further enhanced in the context of developmental physiology. The adaptation of young athletes to gradually and steadily increasing physical activity both facilitates the development of their motor potential and can overload immature systems, particularly the immune system. These and other factors determine the relevance of studying the adaptation of adolescents to intense physical activity—cross-country skiing.

Relevance of the study. The human body's adaptation to intense physical activity is a key issue in muscle physiology and sports medicine. This issue's significance is further enhanced in the context of developmental physiology. The adaptation of young athletes to gradually and steadily increasing physical activity both facilitates the development of their motor potential and can overload immature systems, particularly the immune system. These and other factors determine the relevance of studying the adaptation of adolescents to intense physical activity—cross-country skiing.

Studies of biochemical, hematological, functional parameters, and heart rate variability (HRV) provide important information about the impact of sports training on various body systems, health, and the physiological mechanisms of human adaptation to physical activity. Analysis of these parameters is used for general assessment of athletes' health and fitness, monitoring doping, iron deficiency, anemia, and immunity.

Many studies devoted to this topic in the physiology of muscle activity have a number of shortcomings. For example, they often rely on cross-sectional comparative analyses, which prevents them from distinguishing the effects of training itself from selection effects. Many longitudinal studies assessing seasonal changes in athletes or the impact of training intensity on certain physiological parameters often lack parallel controls, which can obscure the true effects of physical training. These and other features may underlie the inconsistency in the results of studies assessing the impact of physical training on the studied parameters. Much of the discrepancy may be due to the athlete's current functional state, the magnitude of previous loads, and different periods of athletic training. Moreover, many studies aimed at uncovering

the physiological mechanisms of adaptation in various body systems are limited to analyzing the data obtained within a single system, which complicates understanding the physiological meaning of many adaptive changes. The causal factors that may underlie these changes remain hidden, as they are often located outside the body system under study.

With this in mind, we conducted a longitudinal study of a number of physiological and biochemical parameters over the annual training cycle of young cross-country skiers and non-athletes. This allowed us to compare athletes with non-athletes during specific periods of the year and to assess the impact of training loads on the bodies of young skiers. Sports training changes significantly over the course of the annual training cycle. Three periods are distinguished in the annual training cycle of cross-country skiers: preparatory, competitive, and transitional. Of these, the competitive period is characterized by increased training and competitive loads and the maximum mobilization of athletes' functional capabilities. The preparatory period (summer-fall) is characterized by a greater proportion of aerobic training, high training volumes, and moderate intensity. The competitive period (winter) is characterized by intensified training with an increase in its intensity and specificity, sometimes a decrease in overall volume, and a predominance of speed-competitive loads. During the transition period, the volume and intensity of exercise decrease, and recovery training predominates. However, in any period, the total weekly volume of physical activity is many times greater than that of non-athletes. We believe that a number of biochemical, hematological, and other parameters will depend on both the specific physical activity and the environmental (seasonal) training conditions during the annual training cycle. This is the focus of this study.

The aim of the work: to study physical performance, heart rate variability, biochemical and hematological parameters during the annual training cycle of young skiers.

Research objectives:

1. To study the indicators of physical performance and anthropometry during the annual training cycle of young skiers.

2. To study heart rate variability (HRV) during the annual training cycle of young skiers. To determine the relationships between changes in biochemical and hematological parameters, on the one hand, and changes in anthropometric parameters, physical performance, C-reactive protein, and heart rate variability, on the other, during the annual training cycle of young skiers.

Study results. For the first time, a comprehensive analysis of the dynamics of anthropometric data, protein, lipoprotein, hematological, and immunoglobulin blood profiles, systemic inflammatory activity, heart rate variability, and aerobic and anaerobic performance was conducted in the annual training cycle of young cross-country skiers, alongside non-athletes.

New data were obtained on the dynamics of anthropometric indicators across the annual cycle in young skiers. During the period of intensified training loads during the competitive winter period, moderate dehydration was observed in the athletes. Conversely, during the transitional warmer period, hydration levels were restored, which was not observed in the control group.

It was established for the first time that an increase in training loads in cross-country skiers during the competitive period leads to a shift in the sympathetic- vagal balance in the regulation of heart rate towards the dominance of sympathetic activity. This is partly due to the

magnitude of physical activity and, partly, to seasonal effects. In the study, it was established for the first time that in athletes during periods of moderate training loads (preparatory and transitional), systemic inflammatory activity, assessed by the level of C-reactive protein, is reduced. An increase in training loads during the competitive period led to an increase in subacute inflammatory activity in athletes within the control values. The dominance of sympathetic activity in the sympathetic-vagal balance had an anti-inflammatory effect. New data were established regarding the dynamics of hematological parameters in athletes: in the preparatory and transitional periods of the annual training cycle, young skiers showed lower levels of RBC and Ht compared to non-athletes, which was due to Autohemodilution. Increased training loads in the winter period were accompanied by an increase in blood hemoglobin concentration, largely due to an increase in the average hemoglobin content in erythrocytes, as well as an increase in the hematocrit level, mainly due to an increase in the mean cellular volume of erythrocytes. These changes in athletes correlated with an increase in physical performance. To identify the physiological significance of an increase in the sympathovagal ratio in the autonomic nervous system and subacute systemic inflammatory activity in athletes during periods of high physical exertion. Based on correlation analysis, it was shown that a moderate increase in inflammatory activity contributes to the maintenance of immunoglobulin levels, as well as a decrease in cholesterol, LDL-C, and fibrinogen levels. An increase in the sympathovagal ratio during this period may play an important role in increasing hemoglobin and hematocrit levels, probably through its effect on erythropoiesis.

The obtained results significantly expand theoretical knowledge on the physiological mechanisms underlying changes in biochemical and hematological parameters, as well as heart rate variability, physical performance, and anthropometric data during the annual training cycle of young cross-country skiers. These findings make an important contribution to understanding the beneficial, anti-atherogenic, and vasoprotective effects of regular physical training. The results of the study can be used in sports medicine and the practice of medical and pedagogical control: in the diagnosis of the state of athletic fitness and training of young athletes.

New information can be used in writing textbooks on the physiology of muscle activity and sports medicine.

Conclusions. The annual dynamics of heart rate variability in athletes reveals a shift in the sympathovagal balance toward sympathetic dominance during the winter competitive period. The annual dynamics of subacute systemic inflammatory activity show a decrease during periods of moderate physical exertion: the preparatory and transition periods, and an increase during the period of intensified training. The annual dynamics of hematological parameters show decreased hematocrit and hemoglobin levels during the autumn preparatory and spring transition periods. During the winter competitive period, a slight increase in these parameters, within control values, occurs, primarily due to the accumulation of red blood cells with increased volume and hemoglobin content in the blood. Correlational relationships between changes in the studied parameters during the competitive and transition periods allow us to conclude that systemic inflammatory activity, sympathovagal balance of the autonomic nervous system, and body composition play an important non-specific role in the regulation of biochemical and hematological parameters.

List of references:

1. Айрапетянц М.Г., Гуляева Н.В. Роль свободнорадикального окисления липидов в механизмах адаптации // Вестник АМН СССР. 1988. - № 11. - С. 47-50.
2. Abduraimovna, A.D., Turg'unboyevna, Y.N. and Rustamovna, Q.S., 2023. QIZLARNI OILA VA JAMIYATDA O 'ZO 'RNINI TOPISHDA PSIXOLOGIK KO 'NIKMA VA MA'NAVIY YETUKLIKNI SHAKLLANTIRISH. Scientific Impulse, 1(7), pp.310-313.
3. ERMATOV, N., KASSYMOVA, G., TAJIYEVA, K., KHASANOVA, M., ALIMUKHAMEDOVA, M., & AZIMOVA, S. (2020). Expression of tissue-specific genes in mice with hepatocarcinogenesis. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research (09752366), 12(3).
4. Ikramova, N. A., Jalolov, N. N., Mirsagatova, M. R., Kasimova, K. T., Sadirova, M. K., & Sultonov, E. Y. (2025, April). AMBIENT TEMPERATURE AND THE RISK OF THERMOREGULATORY DISORDERS AMONG TRAFFIC POLICE OFFICERS: AN EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS. International Conference on Advance Research in Humanities, Applied Sciences and Education.
5. Ikramova, N. A., Mirsagatova, M. R., Jalolov, N. N., Kasimova, K. T., Sultonov, E. Y., & Sadirova, M. K. (2025, April). THE EFFECT OF THERMAL LOAD ON THE BODY OF OUTDOOR WORKERS: ANALYSIS BASED ON MEDICAL AND HYGIENIC INDICATORS. International Conference on Advance Research in Humanities, Applied Sciences and Education.
6. Kamilova, D. N., Saydalikhujaeva, S. K., Abdashimov, Z. B., Rakhmatullaeva, D. M., & Tadjieva, X. S. (2021). Employment relations and responsibilities of medical institutions workers in a pandemic in Uzbekistan. Journal of Medicine and Innovations, 2(13-1).
7. Kamilova, D. N., Saydalikhujaeva, S. K., Rakhmatullaeva, D. M., Makhmudova, M. K., & Tadjieva, K. S. (2021). Professional image of a teacher and a doctor. British Medical Journal, 1(4), 4-14.
8. Masharipova, R. Y., & Khasanova, G. M. (2020). Improvement of motor fitness of dental students in the process of physical education classes. Bulletin of Science, 5(3), 101-104.
9. Masharipova, R., Togaynazarov, S., Pakhrudinova, N., Khasanova, G., & Abdurahimov, B. (2020). The main factors of formation and physical culture in society. Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy, 11(12).
10. Qosimova, X. T., Ikramova, N. A., Juraboyeva, D. N., & Mukhtorova, D. A. (2025, March). THE ADVERSE EFFECTS OF SMARTPHONES ON COGNITIVE ACTIVITY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS AND WAYS TO MITIGATE THEM. In The Conference Hub (pp. 76-79).
11. Sadullayeva, X. A., Salomova, F. I., & Sultonov, E. Y. (2023). Ochiq suv havzalari muhofazalash ob'ekti sifatida. In V международная научно-практическая конференция «Современные достижения и перспективы развития охраны здоровья населения.
12. Sadullayeva, X. A., Salomova, F. I., Mirsagatova, M. R., & Kobiljonova Sh, R. (2023). Problems of Pollution of Reservoirs in the Conditions of Uzbekistan.
13. Salomova, F. I., & Kosimova, H. T. (2017). RELEVANCE OF STUDYING INFLUENCE OF THE BONDS OF NITROGEN POLLUTING THE ENVIRONMENT ON HEALTH OF THE POPULATION SUFFERING CARDIOVASCULAR ILLNESSES (REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN). In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF THE PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF MODERN SCIENCE AND EDUCATION (pp. 81-83).
14. Salomova, F. I., Ahmadaliev, N. O., Sadullaeva, K. A., & Sherkuzieva, G. F. (2022). Dust storm and atmosphere air pollution in Uzbekistan.

15. Saydalikhujaeva, S. K., & Rustamova, H. Y. (2022). Motivation and satisfaction with the professional activities of nurses anesthetists. *MedUnion*, (1), 163-169.
16. Saydalikhujayeva, S. K., Kosimova, K. T., Mamadzhonov, N. A., & Ibragimova, S. R. (2020). The role of modern pedagogical technologies in improving the system of higher medical education in the republic of Uzbekistan. *New Day in Medicine*, 1(29), 85.
17. Saydalikhujayeva, S. K., Kosimova, K. T., Mamadzhonov, N. A., & Ibragimova, S. R. (2020). The role of modern pedagogical technologies in improving the system of higher medical education in the republic of Uzbekistan. *New Day in Medicine*, 1(29), 85.
18. ShR, K., Mirrakhimova, M. H., & Sadullaeva, H. A. (2022). Prevalence and risk factors of bronchial asthma in children. *Journal of Theoretical and Clinical Medicine*, 2, 51-56.
19. Tadjieva, K. S. (2024). USING SITUATIONAL TASKS TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING MEDICAL CHEMISTRY. *Web of Teachers: Inderscience Research*, 2(1), 64-68.
20. Tadjieva, K. S., Kosimova, K. T., & Niyazova, O. A. (2025). THE ROLE OF AIR POLLUTION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES.
21. Tursunov, D., Sabiorva, R., Kasimova, X., Azizova, N., & Najmiddinova, N. (2016). Status of oxidant and antioxidant systems in alloxan diabetes and ways its correction. In *Science and practice: a new level of integration in the modern world* (pp. 188-190).
22. АБДУЛЛАЕВА, М., & ТАДЖИЕВА, Х. (2023). ИЗУЧЕНИЕ РАСТВОРИМОСТИ СИСТЕМ: КАЛИЕВАЯ СОЛЬ-ОДНОЗАМЕЩЕННЫЙ УКСУСНОКИСЛЫЙ МОНОЭТАНОЛАММОНИЙ-ВОДА. Международный центр научного партнерства «Новая Наука»(ИП Ивановская ИИ) КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ: НАУЧНЫЙ ДЕБЮТ 2023 Петрозаводск, 03 декабря 2023 года Организаторы: Международный центр научного партнерства «Новая Наука»(ИП Ивановская ИИ).
23. Акромов, Д. А., & Касимова, Х. Т. (2017). Результаты изучения токсикологических свойств фунгицида "Вербактин". *Молодой ученый*, (1-2), 2-3.
24. Ахмадалиева, С. У., & Машарипова, Р. Ю. ОСНОВЫ ЗДОРОВОГО ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ СТУДЕНТА МЕДИКА. ББК: 51.1 л0я43 С-56 А-95, 228.
25. Балтабаев, У. А., Джураев, А. Д., & Таджиева, Х. С. (2008). Реакции фенилизотиоцианата с α -аминокислотами. *Жур. Химия и химическая технология*, 1, 39-42.
26. Денисова, У. Ж., & Ахмадалиева, С. У. (2019). МЕТОДЫ, ПОВЫШАЮЩИЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЕ ВОСПИТАНИЕ СТУДЕНТОВ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ СИСТЕМЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. In *ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ* (pp. 141-143).
27. Денисова, У. Ж., & Машарипова, Р. Ю. (2019). Изучение взаимосвязи между морфометрическими характеристиками телосложения баскетболисток 16-18 лет и показателями физической подготовленности. *Вестник науки*, 5(12), 17-22.
28. Денисова, У. Ж., & Машарипова, Р. Ю. (2022). ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ОБМАННЫХ ДЕЙСТВИЙ В СОРЕВНОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ БАСКЕТБОЛИСТОВ 1-КУРСА НА ОСНОВЕ ПОДВИЖНЫХ ИГР. *Вестник науки*, 4(1 (46)), 18-24.
29. Камилова, Д., Сайдалихужаева, Ш., Абдашимов, З., Рахматуллаева, Д., & Таджиева, Х. (2021). Трудовые отношения и обязанности работников медицинских учреждений в условиях пандемии в узбекистане. *Медицина и инновации*, 1(2), 13-19.

30. КАМИЛОВА, Д., САЙДАЛИХУЖАЕВА, Ш., МАХМУДОВА, М., РАХМАТУЛЛАЕВА, Д., & ТАДЖИЕВА, Х. (2022). ИНСОН САЛОМАТЛИГИ ВА ТИББИЙ КЎРИКНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ. Журнал " Медицина и инновации", (3), 143-162.
31. Каримов, В. В., & Машарипова, Р. Ю. (2021). Метод «Джит Кун До» в учебном процессе на занятиях по физической культуре для студентов-стоматологов. Вестник науки, 4(12 (45)), 32-36.
32. Машарипова РЮ, Рожкова АС. Использование нетрадиционных видов гимнастики для оптимизации занятий физической культурой в вузе. InСборник научных трудов I-Международная научно-практической онлайн-конференция «Актуальные вопросы медицинской науки в XXI веке». УДК 2019 (Vol. 6, pp. 613-615).
33. Машарипова, Р. Ю. (2020). Повышение специальной двигательной активности студентов-стоматологов. Наука, образование и культура, (8 (52)), 51-53.
34. Машарипова, Р. Ю. (2022). PhD, ассистент кафедры общественного здоровья, управления здравоохранением и физической культуры Ташкентский государственный стоматологический институт (г. Ташкент, Узбекистан). ВЕСТНИК НАУКИ.
35. Машарипова, Р. Ю. (2022). АНАЛИЗ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВЛЕННОСТИ СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫХ АТЛЕТОВ-ГИМНАСТОВ. Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS), 2(5), 730-737.
36. Машарипова, Р. Ю., & Хасанова, Г. М. (2020). Повышение двигательной подготовленности студентов-стоматологов в процессе учебных занятий физической культурой. Вестник науки, 5(3 (24)), 101-104.
37. Машарипова, Р. Ю., Тангиров, А. Л., & Мирзарахимова, К. Р. (2022). Пути повышения эффективности решения социальных проблем детей с ограниченными возможностями в условиях первичного медико-санитарной помощи. Scientific approach to the modern education system, 1(10), 124-127.
38. Пахрудинова, Н. Ю., Хасанова, Г. М., & Машарипова, Р. Ю. Хореография и здоровый образ жизни. ББК: 51.1 л0я43 С-56 А-95, 278.
39. Рустамова, Х. Е., Нурмаматова, К. Ч., & Машарипова, Р. Некоторые аспекты состояния здоровья населения Узбекистана. ББК, 51, 118.
40. Сайдалихужаева, Ш. Х. (2020). Professional risks in the activities of nurses. on the example of 3rd clinics Tashkent medical academy. Молодойученый.–2020, 52(342), 60-62.
41. Сайдалихужаева, Ш. Х., Косимова, Х. Т., Мамаджанов, Н. А., & Ибрагимова, Ш. Р. РОЛЬ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ДАЛЬНЕЙШЕМ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИИ СИСТЕМЫ ВЫСШЕГО МЕДИЦИНСКОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН.
42. Сайдалихужаева, Ш., & Рустамова, Х. (2021). Синдром эмоционального выгорания у медицинских сестер-анестезистов. Медицина и инновации, 1(2), 9-12.
43. Таджиева, Х. С. (2022). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ МЕТОДА ПРОБЛЕМНЫХ СИТУАЦИЙ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ХИМИИ. In Kimyo va tibbiyot: nazariyadan amaliyotgacha (pp. 205-208).
44. Таджиева, Х. С. (2023). МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМНОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В МЕДИЦИНСКОМ ВУЗЕ. West Kazakhstan Medical Journal, (3 (65)), 170-175.
45. Таджиева, Х., & Юсупходжаева, Х. (2023). Особенности преподавания медицинской химии в современных условиях на лечебном и педиатрическом факультетах

медицинских вузов. Современные аспекты развития фундаментальных наук и вопросы их преподавания, 1(1), 119-124.

46. Хасанова, Г. М., & Машарипова, Р. Ю. (2021). ХОРЕОГРАФИЧЕСКАЯ И АКРОБАТИЧЕСКАЯ ПОДГОТОВКА НА НАЧАЛЬНОМ ЭТАПЕ ПОДГОТОВКИ В ТРАМПОЛИНЕ. Academic research in edu

